

Preferred English language learning strategies among undergraduate EFL students: A Voice from Indonesia

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The high demand for English proficiency in the globalization era has led EFL learners to adopt various strategies to enhance their language skills. This research aims to investigate the kinds of English language learning strategies employed by Indonesian EFL university students. A descriptive quantitative method employing a five-point Likert scale was used to collect data from 70 English Department students purposively selected from several universities in Indonesia. Results of the research revealed that metacognitive strategies become the most frequently used strategies in English language learning. The strategies help the learners organize their learning through planning, centering, monitoring and evaluating how well they have done in the learning process. It means that the learners possess self-awareness to regulate their own learning and can manage their intrinsic motivation for learning. The result of the study has a significant implication for teachers in that they can adjust the learning materials based on the preferred strategies, and the students can also expand their learning strategies according to the strategies they already used.

Keywords: Direct Learning Strategies; Foreign Language Learning Strategies; Indirect Learning Strategies; Language Learning Strategies; SILL Questionnaire

1. Introduction

Foreign Language Learning (FLL) or Second Language Learning (SLL) is noted as a conscious process by which people learn and absorb a second or foreign language in a certain situation. According to Sun (2019), the terms FLL and SLL address the process of learning another different language—second, third, or fourth language which is not one’s native or mother tongue—after learning his native language or first language (L1) in both formal and informal settings.

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Since language learning is seen as a conscious and planned action to learn a new language, EFL students must employ several strategies in mastering it. Sartika et al., (2019) claim that good language learners tend to employ numerous kinds of language learning strategies to grasp, absorb, digest, and master new languages they are learning compared to those who are bad language learners. Moreover, Cohen (2011) clarifies that language learning strategy is claimed to be significant for students in order to overwhelm any difficulties and also to challenge them to master a new L2 if they can apply it appropriately.

In Indonesian contexts, researches under the umbrella of L2 learning have gained a lot of attention from many scholars over decades (Alfian, 2021). Copious researches with numerous different concerns are done to see how Indonesian learners deal with L2 language learning, especially English. For instance, Aunurrahman et al. (2013) who examined first year college students using of the SILL questionnaire concluded that social strategies are the most widely used strategies by the students, followed by metacognitive, cognitive, affective, compensation, and memory strategies. In addition, Anam and Stracke (2016) did their LLS research to find out the relationship between LLS and self-efficacy beliefs among primary school graders. Result shows that young learners are keen on using socio-affective strategies rather than cognitive strategies by which they can cooperate or work with other classmates. Later, Ajeng (2017) worked on her LL research and the finding shows that male students tend to use metacognitive and social strategies compared to the females, yet the similarity relies on the frequent use of cognitive strategies by both genders. Similarly, Tanjung (2018) conducted her research on how age among university level students interferes with their LLS. Results from the SILL questionnaire showed that age truly influences the students to select different kinds of LLSs. Along the same lines, research finding from Syafryadin (2020) reveals that many high school students used metacognitive strategies when they attempted to organize and evaluate proper strategies to be employed in L2 learning.

To be exact, the most relevant study under LLS research conducted in Aceh Province is the one conducted by Nasir et al. (2016), and the participants of their research are first grade students of senior high school. They used 30 items from the SILL questionnaire to be answered by successful and unsuccessful learners in the first grade of senior high school grouped based on their English test scores. The result reveals that successful learners tend to use language learning strategies more frequently compared to those who are unsuccessful learners.

On the contrary, our research is notably dissimilar to the previous ones in several ways. Firstly, this research focuses on middle and advanced levels of

university students—i.e., Third-, fifth-, and seventh-year students in several universities in Aceh Province. Secondly, the research locations of those researches vary within Indonesia, but our research focuses on some university students in Aceh Province—especially English Department students. Lastly, there are many more items in the instrument used in our research, so it is supposedly an extensively valuable measure for providing a fundamental comprehension of LLS patterns among Indonesian university students who have been learning English for a longer time. Using the SILL Questionnaire (version 7.0), this research intends to investigate and analyse the use of genuine strategies of second language learning among English Department students as an attempt to master the second or foreign language in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The researchers formulated the following research questions:

1. To what extent do undergraduate EFL students in Indonesia use direct and indirect foreign language learning strategies?
2. What is the most frequently used foreign language learning strategy among undergraduate EFL students in Aceh, Indonesia?

The research objectives are to measure the level of foreign language learning strategies—direct and indirect learning—used by Indonesian EFL undergraduate students and to investigate the most frequently used strategy among them. The study is meant to be a meaningful reference both for students and educators. It is assumed that students might use the results of this research to monitor and be aware of their English learning style in order to improve their competence in the language. Likewise, educators might find this research relevant to increasing and motivating the quality of English language teaching and learning processes in classroom settings based on students' preferred strategies.

2. Background

Learning strategies are closely associated with learning styles in that both of them eventually help the field of language learning as well as language acquisition. The terms must not be used interchangeably since learning styles constitute a broader term in reflecting the compounded manner in which learners believe, process, cumulate, and recall what they already learn (James & Gardner, 1995; Oxford, 2001, 2003). Meanwhile, learning strategies portray more specific ways or motions employed consciously by learners by which they will find themselves more enjoyable in empowering and recalling the L2 proficiency independently—called learner-centered instruction (Boonma & Swatevacharkul, 2020). Learning styles, similarly, are grouped into three main categories: cognitive, personality, and sensory. These notions have their own

specific subgroups certainly (Dornyei, 2005; Oxford, 2011). On the contrary, learning strategies are notable to possess two major groups: direct, and indirect strategies—leaning on to each other (Oxford, 1990).

In addition, research in the field of language considers language learning strategies as an important factor in mastering L2 (Putro et al., 2022). Since it is not sincerely acquired like first or native language where the speakers or learners unconsciously process any input from surrounding to be intake effortlessly, it indeed requires a massive, strong, and self-motivated desire to be learned consciously by using every possible strategy (Alfian, 2021).

The earliest research on language learning strategies was initiated in the early 1970s (Hardan, 2013) when two researchers, Rubin (1975) and Naiman et al. (1975), made a list of strategies employed by good learners who were successful in the L2 learning. Based on those strategies, the researchers classified two groups of learners—poor and good language learner—in their studies. They, then, claimed that those who use many kinds of certain strategies will likely be successful in LL compared to those who do not.

Later on, O'Malley and Chamot (1990) came up with a new theory of LL in which they classify learning strategies into three main classes: cognitive, metacognitive, and socio-affective. The classification was remarkable enough in LL study since it gives more detail classification of specific strategies. Next, Oxford (1990) completes the previous classification to be more detailed; she elaborates six notions: memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective, and social strategies. Oxford strongly perceives that good learners always have abundant strategies, inside and outside themselves, to equip and enhance their proficiency in L2 learning. Predicated on this assumption, we considered it essential to carry on the present research as an attempt to fill the gap in Indonesia, to respond to the limitations of previous ones, and to provide an additional reference for those who put lots of interest in LLS among EFL students.

Gaining a greater spotlight over decades, the focus of language learning is not merely centred on teachers; it turns to be learner-centred in that it emphasizes the exploration of any strategies used in learners' language learning, how learners deal with the new language learning experience, and how they digest the information. These are some of the considerations in the field (Murat, 2000). The strategies deployed by students could also lead to what might be seen as autonomous learning in that students encourage or motivate themselves by eagerly using various types of language learning strategies as an attempt to empower their own ability in mastering L2 (Ao & Jamir, 2022).

As for direct language learning strategies, they assist learners to keep and recall knowledge of second language learning. There are three types of direct

learning strategies: memory, cognitive, and compensation. Each of them, in turn, has different definite sub-strategies which learners could employ during their learning of English based on their preferences as an attempt to improve their English competency.

Memory strategy is one of the direct strategy categories. Oxford (1990) says that memory strategies mean keeping new information in the long-term memory and recalling it whenever needed. It relates to grammatical rules and vocabulary memorization (Umamah & Cahyono, 2020). There are, moreover, nine statements of self-report within the SILL questionnaire, grouped into four sets of classification: creating mental linkage, applying image and sounds, reviewing well, and employing actions.

Later, cognitive strategies are mental processes in which target language is manipulated by repeating, analyzing, and summarizing (Rohaeti et al., 2019). Those three steps are the most popular strategies in language learners since every single new thing learned in the L2 must be performed in the way of practicing which can be realized by repeating frequently—such as receiving and sending message in searching for main idea through skimming and scanning during reading skill performance, and creating structure for input and output in producing various kinds of new expressions.

Further, compensation strategies are remarked as a guessing strategy among learners who have insufficient proficiency of L2. It means that learners try to solve L2 problems by guessing meaning from context despite limitation of knowledge. The strategy is commonly magnified by adult learners when they find difficulties or struggles in translating L2 vocabulary or phrases and they link their own life experiences to examine data by guessing. The strategies classify into two sets: guessing intelligently in listening and reading, and overcoming limitations in speaking and writing (Hardan, 2013; Oxford, 1990; Samida, 2012).

Indirect Language Learning Strategies, on the other hand, play an important role in language learning since they can get along with direct ones (Hwang et al., 2021). Indirect strategies regulate, support, and manage language processes. There are three major subgroups of indirect strategies: metacognitive, affective, and social. They are claimed to bring about huge impacts on LL.

Metacognitive strategies are best known in the way of learners' piloting learning. It means that learners freely coordinate or manage their own learning through arranging and planning; they use 'evaluating' as the final stage of self-learning (Ahmed, 2021). To be exact, arranging and planning might be used by learners to decide what skills they desire to develop the most, so they can put a lot of effort to improve the skills that they lack. It is, therefore, very crucial to

crosscheck what they already gain and digest during the arranging and planning phase, hence evaluating is considered essential to run in order to monitor the learning progress.

Further, Sugiarta et al., (2021) claim that affective strategies which strongly relate to emotion, attitude, motivation, and values are considerably crucial factors in LL. The strategies include lowering anxiety, self-motivation, and controlling emotions. Good learners commonly can manage those emotion sides to decrease negative thoughts and establish positive thinking to help them respond well to LL.

Lastly, according to (Wei et al., 2021) social interactions are very helpful in LL context since good communication to share information only takes place among people with good interaction. Therefore, social strategies help learners to gain more knowledge from outsiders, and it can be done by asking people some meaningful questions, working with others to increase self-esteem and minimize competitions through information sharing within a group though showing empathy to others by showing interest in understanding others' feeling to build up a better cultural understanding.

3. Method

This research was carried out using a descriptive quantitative design which used a series of questionnaires to collect primary data from respondents and was presented in percentage form. Quantitative research is a type of research that focuses on collecting numerical data in order to conduct deep statistical analyses. One of the major trait of quantitative research is the use of questionnaires as its primary instrument to collect data from samples or respondents while qualitative research is mainly the descriptive study of phenomena or distributions of variables. Qualitative research entails explaining but not attempting to manipulate variables (Ary et al., 2019). As such, the present study is basically quantitative.

3.1. Participants

The participants were male and female students from five universities in Indonesia. The sampling technique used to collect data from those respondents was volunteer-based purposive sampling through the determination of some criteria prior to the study to meet the research need. The participants had to be from among English department students since they spend a lot of time learning foreign languages, and they were not supposed to be first-year students in the department, so the students in semesters three, five, and seven were sampled for the study. Overall, seventy ($N = 70$) students participated in the research.

3.2. Instrument

Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) developed by Oxford (1990) is the most popular questionnaire used to investigate L2 learning among learners since it is claimed to be the most comprehensive one to evaluate foreign language learning strategies (Amerstorfer, 2018; Bessai, 2018; Mizumoto & Takeuchi, 2018; Nemati et al., 2010; Zou & Lertlit, 2022). The 7.0 version of the SILL questionnaire has two major sections—direct and indirect strategies—and each of the strategies is branched into three subgroups. Direct strategies include several notions: memory strategies, cognitive strategies, and compensation strategies. Indirect strategies also comprise three parts: metacognitive strategies, affective strategies, and social strategies.

SILL consists of 50 items: memory strategy (question no 1-9), cognitive strategy (question no 10-23), and compensation strategy (question no 24-29) tap direct strategies. Meanwhile, metacognitive strategy (question no 30-38), affective strategy (question no 39-44), and social strategy (question no 45-50) measure indirect learning strategies.

3.3. Procedure

The data were collected through several steps. As mentioned earlier, the sampling technique applied in this study is volunteer-based purposive sampling, so there are some steps of the workflow which the researchers combined within the study. Firstly, the researchers set some specific requirements for selecting the participants (purposive). Later, they shared the information and invitation or call for participants to the population that met the criteria which had been determined (voluntary). From the population who meets the requirements, then, the researchers selected some of them who volunteered to participate in this study (voluntary and purposive).

Finally, all of the items in the questionnaire were typed into a Google Form. It was done due to the efficiency considerations: it would be more effective, faster and more accessible. The hyperlink to the form, then, was shared with all of the respondents, and the feedback was directly recorded on the form.

The respondents were asked to rate their use of language learning techniques on a five-point Likert Scale ranging, namely (1) never or almost never true of me, (2) usually not true of me, (3) somewhat true of me, (4) usually true of me, (5) always or almost always true of me. In order to make for the respondents easier to answer, all of the items in the questionnaire had been translated into Indonesian language.

After collecting the data, the researchers reviewed all of the data which were taken from the Google form responses. Later, the collected data were analysed using some formula such as average, percentage, and mean score. Finally, all of

the results, according to their scale results, were classified into some categories based on SILL Profile of Result proposed by Oxford (1990). Table 1 displays Oxford's SILL profile results.

Table 1
SILL Profile of Result

Category	Description	Scale
High	Always or almost always used	4.5 to 5.0
	Usually used	3.5 to 4.4
Medium	Sometimes used	2.5 to 3.4
Low	Generally, not used	1.5 to 2.4
	Never or almost never used	1.0 to 1.4

4. Results

After converting SILL responses to percentages, the results for direct learning strategies students said they would use in second language learning were calculated. Mean score were calculated and the results were juxtaposed to SILL profile scales (Table 1 above) to determine the participants' level for each subcategory. See Table 2.

Table 2
The Rank Order of Students' Direct Learning Strategies

No	The Strategies	Mean SILL Profile Scores	Level
1.	Memory Strategy	3.16	Medium
2.	Cognitive Strategy	3.23	Medium
3.	Compensation Strategy	3.32	Medium

All types of direct learning strategies were at medium level based on SILL profile scores (i.e., 2.5 to 3.4). This indicates that English department students from those different universities sometimes used memory, cognitive, and compensation strategies in second language learning.

Their use of memory strategy reached 3.16 which is a medium level of SILL rank. Based on SILL profiles, this level is where students 'sometimes' used memory strategy in learning second language. This strategy positively contributes to the acquisition of new vocabulary, retention, and production as it enables the learners to learn the language more easily, effectively and in a self-directed way (Balini & Jeyabalan, 2018). It could be seen from percentage result of the first SILL item that 25 students with the highest percentage (35.71%) chose 'sometimes' on item 1: "I think of relationships between what I already know and new things I learn in the SL." The next item also showed an important result in that 25 students (35.71%) picked 'sometimes' on the

statement, "I use new SL words in a sentence so I can remember them." this also had a high frequency. This means that most of students 'sometimes' used new L2 words to make a sentence. This is a reflection of arranging things in order as a memory strategy in LL.

The largest number who chose 'sometimes' (with 35.71% and 25 occurrence) was also seen on item number 7: "I physically act out new SL word". This indicated that sometimes they acted new L2 vocabulary which involves both speech and physical movement as the way to keep and recall their knowledge of second language learning. Memory strategy includes arranging things in order, making association, and reviewing. Through it, students correlate their L2 vocabulary with images and sounds that can make them easy to remember. Thus, applying image, reviewing, and acting the L2 words are reflections of this subcategory.

Likewise, the cognitive strategy mean score of 3.23 in this study was labelled as medium in accordance with SILL profile scores. This strategy is suitable for students who follow some activities, including clarifying and verifying, guessing or doing inductive exploration, reasoning deductively, practicing, memorizing to remember, and monitoring (Wirahyuni & Martha, 2022). There were 14 items for this strategy on which most of the respondents had selected 'sometimes used'. It was evident in the percentage of item number 10 that 18 students (25.71%) said that they 'say' or 'write' new SL words several times. Similarly, the next SILL item proved 24 respondents (34.28%) agreed that sometimes they tried to talk like native speakers as an effort in enhancing their L2 ability. The highest frequency was also shown in option 'sometimes' where 20 students (28.57%) claimed that they sometimes make conversation in SL. These activities are forms of cognitive strategy by which learners keep practicing and repeating L2 frequently. This shows that students sometimes used LL strategies such as producing new SL words frequently, speaking like native speakers, and making dialogue. These are forms of cognitive strategy in which L2 must be practiced frequently.

Additionally, the third graph displays compensation strategy at medium rank (when compared to SILL profile scores with the mean score of 3.32). This kind of strategy is extremely useful as a guidance to avoid communication gap in speaking activities (Syafryadin, 2020). It was found that English department students sometimes used the compensation strategy (such as guessing) to overcome their difficulties due to lack of proficiency. Evidently, the finding from SILL item 27 shows there were 16 students (with maximum percentage 22.85%) who chose 'sometimes' on the questionnaire item "I read SL without looking every word." This confirms that they sometimes read all words and made a guess instead of searching for meaning. Likewise, the occurrence on 'sometimes' appears 18 times (with the greatest percentage 25.71%) on SILL

item number 28: “I try to guess what other person will say next in the SL.” This means students also used the guessing strategy when they did not know the meaning. This strategy is commonly utilized by L2 learners when they find obstacles in translating words or phrases.

In accordance with previous studies, this finding confirms Aunurrahman et al. (2013) who used the same framework of SILL and showed memory, cognitive, and compensation strategies were not the commonly used strategies in students’ LL, and that they ‘sometimes’ used them. That research found that social strategy was most commonly used by English learners followed by metacognitive, cognitive, compensation, and memory strategies. On the other hand, our finding contrasts with Manda et al (2022) who claimed that the compensation strategy is very effective to increase students’ English skills, especially in reading comprehension. The better compensation strategies are applied by the students, the better they achieve reading comprehension skills.

As such, English department students from different universities in Indonesia ‘sometimes’ used memory, cognitive, and compensation strategies in learning English as a second language—including linking their previous knowledge with new things they learn in SL, using new words to make sentences so that it can be easily remembered, producing L2 words in speaking and writing, making conversation in SL, and guessing words from their contexts as a relief when they find difficulty in meaning.

As for indirect learning strategies, the subcategory of metacognitive strategies is probed by SILL items number 30 to 38, the affective strategies are measured by SILL items number 39 to 44, and the social strategies are tapped by SILL items number 45 to 50. Our study findings are displayed in Table 3. Students’ levels of strategy use are based on Oxford’s SILL profiles.

Table 3
The Rank Order of Students’ Indirect Language Learning Strategies

No	The Strategies	Mean Scores	Level
1.	Metacognitive Strategies	3.62	High
2.	Affective Strategies	3.30	Medium
3.	Social Strategies	3.38	Medium

As shown from the data above, according to SILL profiles, the indirect Language Learning Strategies most often used by the students is the metacognitive subcategory of strategies with the mean score of 3.62 that reads as the High level of strategy use. It means that the students of the English Department from the universities were very good at self-monitoring to empower their second language learning. They were inclined to use metacognitive strategies when learning English. As previously stated, indirect strategy is the most important

one because it supports, regulates, and manages language learning processes (Hwang et al., 2021). It is divided into metacognitive, affective, and social strategy types (Oxford, 1990).

Our data indicated that metacognitive strategy is at the highest rate of SILL profile which translates into the fact that it was most commonly used by the students in learning the TL. It can be seen in SILL item number 33, "I try to find out how to be a better learner in SL," where 27 students (38.57%) chose 'always used'. Likewise, SILL item number 38 showed that 26 students (37.14%) stated that they 'always' think of programs in learning SL. This shows that students are good at managing their L2 learning processes.

Linking to previous studies, this finding is in line with Syafryadin (2020) who claimed that metacognitive strategy is the high dominant one in learning strategies which help the learners to organize their learning through planning their learning, monitoring, and evaluating how well they have done in the learning of a second language. It means they like linking new information they acquire to what they have already learned and stored in their long-term memory; this is how they attempt to self-monitor in language learning (cf. Oxford, 1990). All of the processes are considered crucial for them to enhance the chances of SL learning successfully and effectively.

The less frequently used indirect strategies 'sometimes' used by the students in our study included 'affective strategies' with mean score 3.30 which is classified into the medium level in accordance with Oxford's SILL profiles. These components are related to emotion, attitude, motivation, and values which are considerably crucial factors in LL. Lowering anxiety, increasing self-motivation, and controlling emotions are part of this strategy (Sugiartha et al., 2021). Generally, good learners are able to manage their emotions to lower negative thoughts and build positive attitude toward LL. Accordingly, this study found that 24 students chose the option 'sometimes used' on SILL items number 39 ("I try to relax whenever I feel afraid of using SL.") and 40 ("I encourage myself to speak SL even when I am afraid of making mistakes.") which gained the highest percentage (34.28%). Most of students try to manage their emotion, so they can perform better in speaking.

The third indirect strategy which obtained the mean score of 3.38 was the social strategy which is categorized as 'medium' level of SILL rank based on Oxford's SILL profile means. Social strategy facilitates learners with interaction and communication to enhance self confidence and at the same time, build cultural understanding (Wei et al., 2021). From the questionnaire result, it was found that 19 students (27.14% of the sample) had answered 'sometimes used' on SILL item number 47: "I practice SL with other students." 24 students (32.85%) also chose the option 'sometimes used' on SILL item number 49: "I

ask questions in SL.” Students in this group sometimes interact with other people to use their English language.

5. Discussion

This research found that the most frequently used strategy by students is the ‘metacognitive’ strategy which is at the high rate of SILL result (3.62), followed by socio, affective, compensation, cognitive, and memory strategies. Our finding is in line with the research done by Alfian (2021) and Hapsari (2019). Metacognitive strategy is the most popular way in L2 learning where students can arrange, plan, and decide what skills to develop the most. They also make evaluation to measure their achievement (Dewi et al., 2018; Hashimoto et al., 2019). This is reflected in some ways such as noticing mistakes, planning schedule for learning, looking for chances to read in the TL, and finding out how to be a better learner of the SL.

There are copious studies that reveal that metacognitive strategies contribute strongly to language performance, involving listening, speaking, reading and writing (cf. Mamo & Regassa, 2025; Qin et al., 2022; Rahimi & Katal, 2012; Salmani Nodoushan, 2008; Sari et al., 2025). In listening skills, metacognitive strategies help EFL learners in increasing their listening competence. Latip et al., (2020) states that there is a significant relationship between metacognitive awareness of listening strategies and the EFL learners’ achievement in the listening skill. Some of the metacognitive strategies, such as problem solving, planning, evaluation, mental translation, and directed attention, which the students prominently use in listening classes directly assist them well in achieving better scores compared to those who do not (Rahimi & katal, 2012; Goh & Hu, 2013).

Moreover, Sari et al., (2025) claim that EFL students who are taught by using metacognitive strategies show better performance in the speaking skill; their fluency, pronunciation and vocabulary use reveals a significant improvement. This strategy also reduces learners’ anxiety (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Sari et al., 2025) and promotes learning autonomy, thus students’ self confidence and awareness are highly promoted in the speaking skill. Daha and Alerwany (2023) add that the strategies help students to increase their speaking skill by some patterns, such as goal setting, self monitoring and reflection towards the performance of their speaking. Our findings lend further support to these claims.

Bouknify (2023) mentions that metacognitive strategies can push forward EFL learners in reading comprehension skill in which the students magnify the strategy before, during and after reading a text. To be precise, before reading a text the students find out the purpose of the reading text, review the type of the text, and guess the context based on images and the title. While reading a text,

moreover, their mental process works well through repeating the information they have read, determining the explicit information and taking notes of the crucial information from the text. Lastly, after they finish reading, they directly summarize what they have read and evaluate their reading performance. In conclusion, metacognition facilitates the students well in comprehending the reading texts.

Lastly, Khan and Kumar (2023) also give their perspective on the advantage of metacognitive strategies in developing students' writing skill. Based on their research results, the strategies are viewed powerful in strengthening the students' critical thinking, and they are able to plan, organize, and develop their ideas into a comprehensive writing. In addition, Pelenkahu et al. (2024) claim that the integration of metacognitive strategies and critical thinking obviously increase students' ability in argumentative writing through planning (i.e., task analysis and gathering relevant information), observing (i.e., reading concentration and statement construction) and evaluating (i.e., controlling and adjusting attitude over the finished task). Our findings lend further support to these claims.

5. Conclusion

This study aimed at investigating English language learning strategies—direct and indirect learning—favoured by Indonesian undergraduate students. The main conclusion of the research is that metacognitive strategies which belong to the indirect learning strategies category are the most frequently used strategies by students in the English Departments of Indonesian schools. Other strategies are all in the medium level with slightly different SILL profile scores.

The finding of the research contributes new useful insights to LLS in relation to EFL university students. It merely adds up to the body of knowledge of strategy inventory for language learning researches and shows that EFL students indeed utilize numerous kinds of strategies to improve their English skills. The result of the study is not meant to generalize the situations in the holistic scope of LLS. The study only portrayed a small group or part of EFL university students in Aceh province in Indonesia. The research has implications for those students and shows that they need to be more aware of the existence of abundant kinds of language strategies which might help them master foreign language and that can be magnified to enhance their English both in learning by themselves and in learning with others.

The study is not without limitations, and its limitations cannot be put aside specifically due to the limited number of respondents. The study only had seventy respondents from different universities in Banda Aceh city. Maybe including many more respondents from other universities both in and out of the province might be more valid for data and conclusions. It is suggested that

those who are keen on conducting further study under the same topic should have more respondents to gain better results and decrease probable bias in data. Further research instruments such as topic-based interviews might also be considered important in gathering further valid data for research.

Authors' Statement

Ida Muliawati contributed to sections 1, 2, 5 and abstract. Lismalinda worked on section 3. Dara Yusnida and Nour Ayouni compiled section 4.

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